

A CRITICAL REVIEW OF THE TRIBOLOGY OF POLYMER COMPOSITES.

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ABSTRACT

This paper is a general review of composite tribology which is rather oriented to polymeric matrices. It is intended primarily as an introduction to the subject for the non-tribologist and offers an indication of the complexity of the subject and a means of rationalising the subject. The central theme is that the tribology of homogeneous contacts is amenable to rationalisation and a framework for interpretation and rationalisation has developed. The nature of Composite systems however are such that they undermine the value of this basic knowledge. Composite tribology is therefore a difficult subject which often falls outside the established framework. It has special features which this review attempts to introduce and emphasize.

INTRODUCTION.

Tribology has a long history but the name is a relatively new acquisition which as yet is not universally accepted. The letter's column of the American Journal of Lubrication Engineering, for example [1], is typical of the current debate in the United States. Is the title "Tribology" a good and sufficient one to describe a diffuse and broad multidisciplinary subject; opinions differ. Arguably the semantics are not important, but this current debate and the history which surrounds it, exemplifies the major problem in reviewing the subject of "Composite Tribology". The word tribology was coined by a physicist [2], all be it one with catholic interests, whose prime initial interest was in the unlubricated friction of metals. The name was popularised by a mechanical engineer with whom the practice of the wear and the lubrication of metals became a major preoccupation [3]. Subsequently the friction, lubrication and wear of other materials such as polymers and ceramics became incorporated. The difficulty was that the experts largely concentrated upon say the fluid lubrication of metals, the boundary lubrication of metals, the abrasion of rubbers, the fatigue of rolling ceramic contacts. Rather restricted but strong bodies of information and experience were accumulated for generic classes of homogeneous materials and as a result the basic approaches were different. Tribology oriented metallurgists, ceramicists

and polymer technologists developed different priorities and communication frameworks. There are common themes in fluid lubrication and contact mechanics, but the dissipative processes which must be invoked to explain friction and wear are, whilst not entirely different, sufficiently so to produce a major intercommunication barrier. The problem with Composite Tribology is that it does require a concerted approach from the experts in the various subjects. The sliding or rolling interface contains materials of characteristically different tribological properties and there is also the internal interfaces between the various phases. The optimisation or the fundamental investigation of a glass filled PTFE for example requires the contributions from ceramic and polymer tribology. Where glass fibres are involved special anisotropic factors are introduced. The internal interfaces are in the domain of composite technology itself.

This review will extend these general points and exemplify some of the many difficulties which arise. We begin with a brief general review of tribology of homogeneous systems under the headings of rubbers, polymers, metals, and ceramics. Some reference to composite systems are introduced at this stage. A distinction will be made between 'rough' and 'smooth' counterfaces and the principles of lubrication are introduced. Selected data are then introduced and discussed for isotropic polymer composites under the heading of particle polymer composites. The following section discusses some additional aspects of oriented polymer composite systems. The paper is concluded with a general discussion of composite tribology with particular emphasis placed upon polymeric matrices. The conclusion returns to the difficulties in describing a system which comprises of materials with inherently different dissipative characteristics and the influence of internal interfaces per se.

TRIBOLOGY.

Conceptually there are two approaches to tribology, Figure 1 although certain subtle items are neglected. The systems approach would attempt to deal with the whole problem and try to avoid discrete subdivisions [4,5]. It is a fine idea which is not practised by fundamentalists but it does have a practical value. The fundamentalist works in the small boxes and attempts to provide the interconnections. We will sketch this approach and begin with friction which introduces the idea of the two model of friction and the importance of counterface topography. In a way it is the fundamentalists desire to work inside the boxes which produces some of the problems in rationalising composite tribology.

Frictional Work.

One can slide or roll or both in a variety of contact configurations. Traditionally, or at least since the Bowden and Tabor monographs [6,7], there have been two basic models available to describe how work is done at interfaces. There are, as we shall see, obvious connections with adhesion science and engineering which are themselves central elements in composite technology [8]. Figure 2 is a schematic diagram of two cases of solid-solid contacts where one body is rigid and hence does not contribute itself to the frictional work and the other is deformable. In Figure 2(a) we have the deformation or ploughing modes where the strain is introduced by the contact geometry; the bulk strain will scale as $E/Y \tan \theta'$ where E and Y are respectively the Young's modulus and the plastic flow stress - Figure 2(c). In Figure 2(b) the strain is introduced by interfacial stresses propagated by adhesive forces; $\theta' = 0'$. Clearly in virtually all cases,

FIGURE 1. Diagrammatic representation of the processes involved in the description of the tribology of polymers.

both processes occur and interact so that the contributions are not simply additive [9,10]. With only a few exceptions, in metal cutting and scratching, the processes are assumed to be non-interacting and the separate contributions derived from various models are summed [10]. This provides the basis of the two term non-interacting model of friction, which sometimes is adopted under other guises. It is a gross approximation which has the virtue of rendering an intractable problem amenable to a first

FIGURE 2. Schematic diagram of the two cases of solid-solid contacts where one body is rigid and the other is deformable.

order rationalisation. Its application in composite systems leads to special difficulties because the model involves a scaling for the thickness of the dissipation zones which may be of the order of the secondary phase sizes.

Ploughing Components.

The ploughing and deformation modes are better understood and can be effectively modelled in many cases. There are several seminal papers, comprehensive texts and reviews on the subject [6,7,11,12,13]. The work input per unit sliding distance ϕ , is a function of the modulus and/or the flow stress depending upon the deformation mode and the contact conditions. The work done is say ϕa where a is a dissipation parameter. The zone where the energy is dissipated is extensive and corresponds to a depth of the order of the contact dimensions. One example will suffice. Figure 3 shows a series of cones sliding upon PMMA as a function of cone angle 2θ , and the friction trace is shown [14]. The contact may be lubricated to remove the adhesion. As θ' increases, the cone angle decreases, various energy dissipation modes are introduced. For small $\tan \theta'$ the deformation is reversible, viscoelastic deformation and the $a = \tan d$, here d is the loss angle. As θ' increases, plastic flow accompanies the viscoelastic processes and work is done by plastic deformation processes; it is approximately W/π

FIGURE 3. Schematic of a series of cones sliding on PMMA, together with representations of the friction-force traces.

$\tan \theta'$. Brittle tearing or cracking work may also occur and this may be evident in the friction trace as stick-slip motion [14,15]. The area shown in Figure 3(a) on the friction-time trace may be attributed to this form of work, although no model is available to quantify its contribution a priori. We can thus subdivide the two component model further by specifying three contributions to the friction work in ploughing; viscoelastic work, plastic work and tearing or brittle work. Figure 4 is an example of the quality of this additivity, based upon first order models for viscoelastic friction, plastic friction and the assumption that a part of the discontinuous friction trace is due to tearing work. This exercise is not really important in itself but it underlines the fact that only a part of the deformation work results directly in damage and hence will generate wear. The total frictional work is of consequence because it defines the interface temperatures; FV , where V is the sliding or rolling velocity, which defines the work done. Virtually all of this work appears ultimately as heat [16]. The temperatures created and their distributions are functions of many variables in particular the thermal conductivity of the bodies [6,7,17]. This fact limits the high speed operation of many systems such as polymeric composites and special design considerations are often necessary to overcome these restrictions. More is said on this topic later.

FIGURE 4. Experimental results from sliding cones of varying included angles over PMMA. Also shown is the breakdown of the frictional work as determined experimentally, into the various modes described in the text.

Adhesion Components.

There is still debate in the literature on the best way to treat this model of frictional energy dissipation. However there is agreement that it is scaled by the real area of contact A , and not the apparent area as is the case for first order treatments of ploughing modes. So the adhesion component is

$$F = A \phi$$

where A may be a function of δ , and δ is just the work done per unit contact area per unit sliding distance. The present authors call δ an interface shear yield stress (interfacial shear stress) and have δ as a function of contact pressure, W/A , sliding velocity and temperature [18]. Tanaka [19] has, in special circumstances, termed it an interfacial viscosity. Other workers have not considered it as a rheological property but related it to a surface energy [20]. The important point here is however that it is an interface property which is conferred upon the system by the outer most layers of the surfaces. A typical figure for the thickness is perhaps a few hundred Angstroms on each surface. In the deformation modes the energy is dissipated over a thickness of the order of the gross contact dimensions. The other general point is that the strains, pressure, temperatures and rates of deformation are much higher in these narrow zones [21]. It has been argued that the properties of δ can be modelled based upon observed bulk deformation behaviour if the contact conditions are extrapolated to those which exist in interface zones [22]. This may be true but generally extensive damage, both mechanical and chemical in nature, occurs in the contact zones and the nature of the interface zones cannot be accurately specified. This is very much the case for multiphase systems such as composites which cannot be assumed to produce interface zones which are simply a reflection of the bulk composition [23-25]. There is also a final and so far intractable problem of unequivocally specifying the real contact area.

To end this section on a less pessimistic note we offer an example of the predictive capacity of the adhesion model for a variety of polymers. If the normal load is high then $A = W/P_0$ here P_0 is a flow stress [6,7]. For polymers $H = 1.5 P_0$, and hence A can be estimated for this case [26]. Studies on thin (100 nm) polymer films show that to a reasonable approximation:-

$$\delta = \delta_0 + \alpha P \quad \text{where } \delta_0 \text{ and } \alpha \text{ are constants [18,27].}$$

Thus:-

$$\mu = F/W = \delta_0 / P_0 + \alpha$$

Thus using thin film and hardness measurements μ can be estimated and compared with results obtained here the same polymers are slid over clean smooth substrates as monolithic samples [28]. Table 1 shows this comparison and substantiates the idea of localised energy dissipation in the interface layers [29]. Although we shall not focus upon the point further these results and others indicate that δ can be measured directly. Where A cannot be equated to W/P_0 we must resort to modelling the contact area or at least its variation with W [11].

The fundamental significance of δ is not of substantial importance in the current context, except for one fact which is intimately involved in broad specification of how the work is done. Like the deformation modes we can specify reversible viscoelastic loss, plastic flow and brittle cracking as first order categories. Again, only two produce damage in the first instance. This is not immediately useful and neglects a core feature of some of the adhesive modes. For some materials, the interface adhesion is so strong that the shear plane is not at the original interface but within the deformable partner. Particles of the softer partner, and indeed the harder partner in some cases, are transferred to the other member. The process may be so pronounced that coherent films are deposited [30-34]. Some polymers, PTFE is the notable example, actually draw out highly oriented layers which are deposited on the counterface [32]. These processes of transfer film formation have many subtle features which are

TABLE 1.

Predictions of the friction coefficient from the adhesion model, using thin film measurements of the interfacial shear strength and hardness values for the various polymers. Experimental values for the polymers sliding against themselves ($\mu(b)$) and smooth glass counterfaces ($\mu(g)$) are also shown.

Polymer	Po(x10MPa)	δ (MPa)	α	$\delta/Po + a$	$\mu(b)$	$\mu(g)$
PTFE	2.27	1.0	0.08	0.12	0.16	0.13
HDPE	3.90	2.5	0.10	0.16	0.15	0.08
LDPE	1.53	6.0	0.14	0.53	0.52	0.42
PP	4.75	5.0	0.17	0.27	0.26	0.26
PMMA	26.8	10	0.36	0.39	0.36	0.41
PS	13.9	4.0	0.45	0.48	0.42	0.45

discussed later. They form the basis of the adhesive or transfer wear modes. They seem restricted to ductile materials where appreciable plastic flow can occur [8,32]. Thus elastomers and ceramics do not exhibit this phenomena in a marked fashion. Elastomers may have surface bloom and become chemically degraded and produce transfer layers of modified materials [33]. Glassy polymers and cross linked resins exhibit interface failures unless high interface temperatures melt or thermally degrade the polymers. These comments would not be particularly significant were it not for the fact that a large fraction of the low friction polymers are also transferring polymers and vice versa [24,35].

We should briefly mention here two other friction dissipative modes which do not fit easily into this picture. They are the Schallamach frictional process and the Coulombic process. The Schallamach wave [15] is a mode 1 reversible adhesion failure which is rather special and is not considered further. The Coulombic mode involves moving asperities over one another and was favoured by Leonardo da Vinci and Coulomb themselves [36,37]. If the asperity slope is θ then $\mu = \tan \theta$ just like the inclined plane experiment. The problem with the Coulomb model is that it is non dissipative, but the essential feature is that it was developed for wood, a fibrous composite. More is said of this later in the context of wood wear and normally oriented fibre composites.

Lubrication of Solids.

Lubrication can be defined or described in a number of ways and the phrase can be usefully extended to include the general topic of the environmental sensitivity of sliding and rolling contacts. There are many reviews available which are either broad, material specific or mechanistic [19,38]. If the solid bodies can be separated by a weak interfacial layer and thereby reduce the extent of solid-solid contact both the friction and the wear are generally reduced. Figure 5 is a summary based upon fluid (thick film) and interfacial (thin film) lubrication. In the fluid film regime the film thickness is a function of the rheology of the fluid and sometimes the mechanical properties of the solids. High quasi hydrostatic

FIGURE 5. Schematic summary of the various modes of lubrication and the material parameters of importance in these contacts.

pressures are produced in the fluid in a transient manner. Thin film or boundary lubrication is a function of the real area of contact A and the interfacial rheology ϕ . The distinction between the two processes is quite blurred in practice as even very low relative velocities will create a thick fluid film [19].

As far as composite tribology is concerned four important points emerge which will be introduced in outline. These are:-

1) the transient hydrostatic pressures in the interface may cause the propagation of cracks at interfaces and as a result wear or damage increases [39].

2) the environment (lubricant) can modify the interfacial adhesion between the phases and promote bulk interfacial failures [8,39].

3) the environment may also modify the nature of the 'third body' and the properties of the transferred layers (see later).

4) the lubrication is also capable of introducing stress fatigue cracking and plastisation of the homogeneous matrix [39].

The fluid will however reduce the surface temperatures and alter the debris expulsion processes (see later).

We can briefly conclude that lubrication (or the environment) will produce a variety of effects, some of which are good and some bad from a practical stand point. One of the virtues of many composite systems is that they are 'self lubricating' and deliberate lubrication can undermine this process. Gardos has recently completed a masterly review of self lubricating composites [24]. The choice of lubricant is important and environmental sensitivity is an important performance variable.

Damage Modes.

The damage modes introduced previously are summarised in Figure 6, under the friction mode subdivisions of adhesion and ploughing [40,41]. Table 2 is an extension of a tabulation produced by Lancaster recently

TABLE 2.

General summary of the damage produced in homogeneous solids, the important material properties, how they lead to specific types of material damage and the interrelationship of these factors.

FIGURE 6. Damage modes induced by friction, subdivided by adhesion and ploughing components.

which emphasises in a general way the damage produced during deformation for homogeneous solids [42]. Lancaster produced this tabulation for abrasive wear (ploughing wear), but it has been extended to cover all damage processes with some extensions. Several features are introduced. Damage is produced by only part of the work input and it is of two kinds; plastic and brittle in the extremes. PMMA was given as an example previously whose three dissipation processes can be abstracted. Thus we have plastic grooving, tearing and cutting as potential wear mechanisms. Figure 6 shows some of these processes in a practical way. As the surface strain will be a function of the asperity slope angle $\tan \theta'$ the damage modes may be more pronounced in ploughing. Nevertheless adhesive induced tractions will produce cracking or tearing; 6(c). The transfer modes will be more likely with ductile solids (low E/Y) and these are incorporated. Where transfer does not occur chemical degradation is an alternative and often accompaniment. The Table 2 and Figure 6 also introduce the idea of subsurface damage; 6(a), 6(c) and 6(b). Significant strain fields are developed in some cases beneath the contact [13]; say Figure 6(b). This has two consequences. First high temperatures may develop and propagate during many repeated deformations. One of the problems in defining damage mechanisms hinges upon the question whether it occurs in a single deformation (or a unit deformation) or as a consequence of multiple deformations (or a fatigue process). The picture today is not clear but for various reasons multiple deformations are generally regarded as being necessary to produce sufficient damage to facilitate the formation of a wear particle [43]. More is said of this later. For the moment it is just necessary to recognise that the selection of the appropriate material parameter requires a pre-judgement of the number of deformations required to induce sufficient damage to produce a debris particle. This may be a low or high cycle fatigue criteria or a simple toughness of fracture mechanics parameter. The problem is also complicated by topographical modifications to the deformable solid; and ridges or prows may well form which can be subsequently removed.

In summary we may note that the friction dissipation mode will define where the energy is dissipated in the contact. Contact mechanics in principle will more precisely define the location of the stress fields and the two term model is a first order approximation which defines two primary regions. The damage modes are a reflection of the mechanical properties although it will generally be unclear whether the damage occurs quickly or in a progressive way. The changing nature of the contact region and the uncertainties which surround such things as the real contact area preclude the use of a precise descriptor.

Interface layers, third bodies, debris entrainment, topographical modifications and wear.

Damage produces debris, and when this is expelled from the contact, wear is produced. Whether the debris is displaced from the contact zone depends upon many factors in particular the contact geometry. In a confined or conforming contact the debris will not be readily displaced [44]. The same will apply to a contact where only microdisplacements occur; the wear produced in these contacts is often termed fretting [45]. This debris accumulating process is less marked in line or non-conforming contacts. These debris particles may act as lubricants, that is weak surface layers which reduce the friction [23,46]. They may modify the surface topography; in some cases make the counterface smoother and in others increase the roughness [24,25,46-48]. There is a school of tribology which emphasises

FIGURE 7. Schematic diagram of some of the discrete sequences envisaged in the formation of the 'third body'.

the critical importance of this third component or body [49,50]. It will be a contact zone of changing morphology, structure, chemistry, particle size and aspect ratio. It will be comminuted and compacted, stretched and rolled by repeated deformations. Figure 7 is a sketch of some of the discrete sequences envisaged although the sequence is artificial. The wear rates observed are a reflection of many interacting processes and a reduction in wear is effected by judicious selection of many variables. Clearly if the damage is reduced, wear is reduced, but other factors influence the damage and the wear [47]. The uncertain multiphase nature of any third body is a major restriction on sensible predictive capacity which is greatly aggravated in composite systems.

In this section we have dealt with what is termed mild or steady-state wear. No exclusive classifications have been offered in this section, but some were introduced in the previous section. Wear is often classified according to the damage mechanism; fatigue wear, and transfer wear, or microcutting for example [51,52]. A comprehensive survey of wear mechanisms based on damage mode has been made by several authors, most recently by Czichos in the context of composites [41]. For composites we shall later invoke damage modes as a basis but use the energy or stress location as the classification: Figure 6. Mild wear is an arbitrary term which conveys the idea of longevity in the components; most of the things we use wear-out eventually. The other wear is severe or catastrophic wear where the components are rendered useless after only a short period of operation. The load bearing capacity or power dissipation threshold is exceeded at the contact under gross failure: it scuffs, seizes, melts or fragments. This is often a themally induced failure and hence the frictional force is an important factor. Many composites are formulated to reduce the frictional work simply for this purpose. A third body is generated to act as a lubricant.

COMPOSITE TRIBOLOGY - a subject in it's own right.

We began by suggesting that the study of composite tribology is

problematical because of the range of material response, dissipative characteristics and damage modes present in a multiphase material. Glass and PTFE are intrinsically different materials tribologically and require rather different conceptual approaches. They dissipate the frictional work and are damaged in different ways. The third body and the topographical modifications introduce a complication of a new dimension. The discontinuities in their mechanical properties at the interfaces undermine the value of simplified contact mechanical treatments. This is particularly so in anisotropic systems. The question then emerges as to whether a knowledge of elemental tribology, say polymer and ceramic tribology, is of value in explaining the tribology of glass filled PTFE. The answer seems to be that what we call elemental tribology provides the framework, the semantics and the first order models, but certain overriding features which exist in composite systems negate a simple translation of this knowledge. You cannot simply add your knowledge of the tribology of glass and PTFE tribology and explain the tribology of glass-filled PTFE without invoking new and specific ideas. Composite tribology like composite materials technology is a subject in its own right. We now offer some examples selected to demonstrate certain principles which apply almost uniquely to composite contacts.

Particle filled systems, nominally spherical inclusions.

Friction.

Our knowledge of friction processes is based upon an arbitrary but proven choice of two dissipation zones. If the scale of the heterogeneity in the composite is less than the scale of these zones then we may comfortably apply the traditional approaches adopted for homogeneous bodies [52]. Unfortunately it seems that this simplification can only be applied to certain ploughing modes. For viscoelastic ploughing we may certainly sometimes use the bulk mechanical properties of the composite to accurately model the frictional work. When ploughing damage occurs the position is far less clear, Freidrich [52] has recently pointed out that this is a rather unexplored area. This topic is discussed later in the context of ploughing wear.

It is of more interest to concentrate upon the interfacial modes of friction where the energy dissipation zone will nominally be much narrower than the size of the discrete phases. There are two general cases which are shown in Figure 8 where the vague notion of hard and soft (or weak and tough) are used. For example, case 8(a) is for glass spheres in PTFE [25], and case 8(b) is PTFE dispersed in PEEK [53]. Other examples are indicated. Case 8(a) and (b) have been well explored for polymer matrices [54-59]. The interface contains both phases in the form of a mixture or 'third body'. The friction is not a great function of the bulk composition simply because the weaker phase is rapidly distributed over the counterface surface and acts as a 'lubricant'. Additivity rules generally don't work although it is tempting to apply them. Based upon the adhesion model we could write that the total friction F as:

$$F = \delta(av) \times A(av) + \delta(s) \times A(s)$$

where $\delta(av)$ and $\delta(s)$ are the interfacial shear strengths of the two phases respectively, likewise the areas $A(av)$ and $A(s)$. If the volume fractions are respectively $V(av)$ and $V(s)$ so that $V(av) + V(s) = 1$. We cannot relate $V(i)$ and $A(i)$ but say $V(i) = K A(i)$, then:

$$F = C' + C''V(s) \quad \text{where } C'' = \delta(s)/K \text{ and } C' = [\delta(s)/K - \delta(av)/K]$$

Equations of this sort are common but their physical significance must be

very questionable.

FIGURE 8. Diagram of the two modes of energy dissipation envisaged in particulate filled composites, for each case of 'hard' and 'soft' phases.

Damage Processes.

The dissipation zone scaling theorem continues to have value and some useful contact mechanical treatments have been applied. The most obvious example is in the viscoelastic deformation process where fatigue crack propagation accompanies the subsurface deformation. The classical example is in the fibrillation of wood [60]. Suh [61] has applied this idea in the context of two composites and described the damage (or wear) as delamination. The Warnop and Archard [62] work on PMMA is a good example of thermally induced subsurface weakening. The subsurface stresses are localised and in composite systems may induce internal interface failures; the surface peels away. The location of the subsurface deformation is primarily a function of the asperity radius and Atack and Tabor used this principle to suggest the optimum asperity size for fibrillating wood pulp.

More intensive stresses will induce cracking or plastic flow. The particles significantly modify the strain fields and provide mechanical discontinuities at the internal interfaces. This is an awkward problem (see Freidrich [52]). For particle filled systems, topographical modifications apart, the abrasive wear will generally increase for composite systems compared with the homogeneous components. The presence of multiple phases almost seems to increase the roughness of the counterface (see later).

So far it appears that the uses of composite systems have no virtues in suppressing damage. This may be so but there are many examples of composite systems where this wear is generally reduced by the introduction of secondary phases. These cases are however either ones where there are topographical modifications or where transfer wear and self lubrication occurs. Recall Figure 8 where the softer phase acts as a lubricant. The fact that the lubrication occurs indicates that one phase is weak and efficiently transfers to the harder phase. The presence of the hard phase inhibits the transfer wear by a number of means not least the fact that the lubricated hard phase wears more slowly. This topic is developed further in the next section.

Wear.

We can begin by commenting that simple additivity rules are unlikely to be applicable. The two main problems are the unknown third body and the prospect of topographical modification. Both are complex problems and one example will suffice to illustrate the difficulties. In Figure 8(b) a hard phase (say glass) is incorporated in a weak phase (say PTFE). The result is that the wear on smooth metallic counterfaces is low and the frictional force is close to the value for PTFE. The composite wear is about three orders of magnitude less than that of the virgin polymer. This result is typical of many systems of this type. What is important in this type of system is the creation of very thin coherent strongly adherent transfer film or third body. The presence of the hard phase achieves this either by creating limited chemical reactions between the polymer and the counterface or by 'hot welding'. Some fillers especially hard fillers, do this well but others such as MoS₂ and graphite do not. They produce thick weakly adherent layers [63]. The general belief is that the transfer layers needs to be strongly attached to the counterface and this prevents further transfer and hence wear [8]. The other wear in this contact is the topographical modification produced by the hard phase. The literature contains many citations on the topic of the optimum roughness for transfer wear [64-66]. For HDPE the value of 0.5 μm Rc is commonly quoted. The hard filler will abrade the counterface and perhaps create this optimum topography. Also the abrasive filler will 'clean' the counterfaces [46,47]. The hardness or abrasion resistance of the counterface and indeed its chemistry may be very important [67].

In this mode of wear lubricants often have the effect of increasing the wear because they appear to reduce the adhesion of the transfer layers to the counterfaces. Abrasive fillers reduce this sensitivity and it is thought that they can remove the weak lubricant layer from the counterface. The ploughing modes of wear have not been widely explored save for the delamination mechanism cited earlier. As with any ploughing mode there is the problem of topographical modification, but with composites the consequences are more acute. The counterface can be polished by hard particles and levelled by the soft matrix.

Non-spherical Inclusions.

In the previous section we have considered spherical inclusions. The same broad conclusions can be applied to short fibre or plate inclusions and unidirectional fibre, parallel and anti-parallel (see below). The matrix determines the tribological performance at low (10%) fibre volumes, whilst at higher (50%) volumes, the reinforcement dominates. The beneficial effects of carbon fibre and the deleterious effect of glass fibres have been demonstrated in a number of studies [46-48,68-71]. There are indications that certain platelets such as mica are more efficient in reducing transfer wear than spherical inclusions but these are unconfirmed [72]. Lancaster [71,73-76] investigated the application of unidirectional carbon fibres to polymer bearings, this provides a classic example of some of the broad features brought out here. A strong association with the tribology of graphites and carbon emerged, with the effects of fibre type, counterface and its topography important in the formation of a transfer film, as well as its interruption by lubricant/environment. Damage modes present in carbon fibre systems have provided support for the delamination theory of wear [61]. Incorporation of a second fibre into the reinforcing system can bring synergistic effects on the wear rate [77]. Optimisation of the beneficial factors can lead to a reduction in wear rate of upto five orders of magnitude [63]. In this section we shall concentrate upon

extended and oriented fibre composites. Figure 9 introduces the usual nomenclature of parallel, antiparallel and normal. An excellent and clear summary of the broad empirical features of the tribological response of these types of systems has been produced recently by Tsukizoe and Ohmae [78] in the book edited by Freidrich.

In this section we will not distinguish friction damage and wear, but concentrate upon a feature which has not been stressed previously; the ultimate load bearing capacity. The general arguments about the scale of the dissipation zone compared with the inclusion size is a good introduction. In the parallel and anti-parallel modes little has changed and the general features of the particle filled systems are applicable. There is obviously more affine connection but the general ideas of delamination, transfer wear and counterface modification will apply. The really interesting configuration, although it is not used in practice, is the normal configuration. At low levels of energy dissipation models 8(a) and (b), may be applicable and perhaps in the mild wear modes the normally oriented glass/PTFE system is more effective than the glass sphere filled system. The glass will have a better heat transmission than the matrix. One of the features of fibre-reinforced systems is their capacity to adsorb an enormous amount of energy in certain deformation modes. Hull's work [79] on the impact of fibre reinforced composites where the impact direction corresponds with the fibre direction is an excellent example. The same thing seems to happen in the sliding of normally oriented composites; they can scuff or fail in a most catastrophic fashion. The orientation produces larger or more dissipative zone adjacent to the contact where a very large amount of energy is dissipated in the destruction of internal interfaces. The paper by Tsukizoe and Ohmae [80] indicates the source of this deformation work. It is interesting at this stage to recall the Coulombic model of friction or at least its pictorial representation [81].

FIGURE 9. Nomenclature of the sense of sliding when using unidirectional fibre for matrix reinforcement, these relate to the relative orientation of the fibres with respect to the sliding direction.

In conclusion to this section we return to the parallel and anti-parallel configurations and indicate some of their additional virtues compared with the particulate analogues. The most obvious one is the mechanical stability of these systems particularly as thin shells or journals, the walls can dissipate heat. A common and favoured system is a glass, PTFE and carbon weave in an epoxy matrix; a hybrid [35,52]. The PTFE is the lubricant as perhaps so is the carbon, glass is the topographical modifier and both the glass and carbon act as effective reinforcing fibres. Internal interfacial adhesion is important to suppress such things as

delamination. The paper by Tsukizoe and Ohmae [80] indicates clearly the importance of good internal interfacial adhesion in defeating wear. Certain extra ingredients may also be useful to modify the chemical erosion of the system or to promote 'good' transfer films; Pb or Sb, Ag oxides are often used.

CONCLUSIONS.

In this review we have focussed latterly upon polymeric composites and neglected other systems. This is natural as less material is available in the literature in other areas. With the exception of cast iron [82] and metal alloys [83,84] there is little work on metal matrices, although some work has been undertaken on fibre reinforced systems [85,86]. In ceramics there is even less [87].

Simplification is at the heart of conventional, tribological thinking for the fundamentalist. Two component non interacting friction models, discrete damage modes and model wear processes are adopted to simplify many intractable problems. In homogeneous systems where heterogeneity scales are small, tribologists have become comfortable with the application of certain empirically based rules and principles. Central to many of these rules are various simplifications based upon the scale of the dissipation zones and the various damage zones involved. In composite systems the value of these arbitrarily defined zones is suspect and this undermines the application of the established principles of tribology to composite materials. The fundamental study and understanding of the tribology of composites is thus naturally limited at the present time as it questions the whole basis of the way in which the subject of tribology is currently treated at a fundamental level. The practitioner is also faced with many problems and relies heavily upon an accumulated empiricism. The major problem, as it is in many tribological systems, is in wear life prediction from model experiments or simulations [35]. For composite systems the difficulty is now acute and the lack of fundamental insights indicates why this is so. What is clear however, is that the development of the understanding of the subtleties of composite tribology will be paralleled with an appreciation of the short comings of our understanding of the subject as a whole, Figure 1.

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